

Connecting Horizons –Memory and Voids in the Paleolithic

CONNECTING HORIZONS

Cover Page:

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CONNECTING HORIZONS seeks to map the intricate history of connectivity through populations' movement and memory horizons, and to reveal how memory and change structure our social, spatial, and temporal furthest reaches, even in the present, to plan for a fragile future.

What are the basic foundations of our hyper-connected world is rooted in what makes us the way we are, yet what these foundations are remains unanswered. When were the earliest long-distance connection networks established? How where they collectively remembered, or forgotten? How did connection and memory adapt to extreme changes such as natural hazards, climate shifts, or large-scale migrations? Did these spatio-temporal connecting horizons persist, transform, or vanish under pressure?

CONNECTING HORIZONS aims to answer these by identifying the emergence, loss, and consolidation of inter-group interactions, and to understand how these—together with memory technologies—have supported the preservation of knowledge about disasters and scarcity as well as exchange of resources, skills and expertise, across interconnected populations.

We finally have the required data and techniques to explore innovative and hypothesis querying how walk-based populations evolved to overcome the fragility of connectivity in a rapidly changing world, and how that essence informs us of our future in particularly vulnerable times. I propose to integrate the growing wealth of archaeological data from the Palaeolithic in Europe, the Middle East, and southeastern Africa, combined with increasingly fine-grained paleoclimatic simulations, niche modelling, paleogeographies, paleogenetic of diseases, transport patterns and cross-cultural comparative baseline among walking-based societies. CONNECTING HORIZONS infers what forms of material exchange and transport can be expected, how such connections are remembered over time, and how they transition into new configurations as material, climatic, and social conditions change.

1.1. Introduction:

The interconnectivity of human populations has been widely examined as a dynamical phenomenon across multiple disciplines (1), yet archaeology has not fully capitalised on its unique capacity to interrogate how connectivity emerges, stabilises, fragments and reconstitutes across deep time (2). Particularly revealing are moments when populations **experimented with transporting and exchanging materials over long distances, weaving and wading an interconnected world under shifting climates and hazards**. Across these transitions, populations depended on effective ways of remembering distant lands, peoples and past events (3–6); these constitute their ‘horizons’. Collective memory is inherently unstable and continuously decays (7–11), systematically reshaping horizons by determining what is remembered, forgotten and avoided—especially under conditions of environmental stress and climatic change (12–14). Memories and movements are, thus, interlinked. Although archaeology is uniquely positioned to reconstruct the deep history of this system, it currently lacks a formal theoretical and modelling framework capable of linking collective memory dynamics to population movements. **I argue that this conceptual gap has significantly constrained our ability to explain how transport was forged, disrupted and re-established through major climatic transitions**, including volcanically induced perturbations (15, 16). CONNECTING HORIZONS directly addresses this limitation by integrating dynamic models of connectivity with empirical archaeological evidence, advancing the proposition that archaeological ‘voids’—spatio-temporal absences often treated as noise—can be read as structured outcomes of collective memory dynamics interacting with hazard exposure. By explicitly mobilising collective memory as a causal variable, CONNECTING HORIZONS establishes a new key explanatory framework for inferring the evolution, stabilisation and loss of connectivity across space and time, positioning archaeology at the forefront of interdisciplinary research on resilience, vulnerability and long-term human adaptation.

CONNECTING HORIZONS fills this gap by conjoining my previous expertise with three complementary domains: i) paleoclimatic reconstructions of natural **hazards, extreme weather and climate fluctuations** at the highest possible resolution; ii) **paleolandscape** modelling to find the most suitable habitat conditions; iii) compilation and systematisation of the range of extremes that **walk-based communities** cope with, in terms of scarcity, distances and remembering.

The overlap of these fields, provides the multidisciplinary platform from which CONNECTING HORIZONS’ main research questions emerge (FIG. 1):

- Q1. How did **natural hazards** erode habitat sustainability depending on subsistence strategies?
- Q2. How stable were **waterbodies** through time and space under extreme climatic variability?
- Q3. How did the diversity of walk-based **transport and exchange** strategies shape what materials were traded and moved across landscapes?
- Q4. How did landscape resources, hazards and past disasters were **remembered** in oral traditions, **influencing the avoidance** of certain areas?

FIG. 1 Diagram summarising the three main areas providing four research questions

Combining multimodal methodologies—theory, data, and modelling—CONNECTING HORIZONS proposes a pioneering approach to investigate how our deeply interconnected world emerged, how it became stable, and how past breakdowns in connectivity or shrinking interaction horizons might be traced in the archaeological and ethnographic record. This project mobilises abundant, yet difficult-to-integrate, evidence to infer how **shared memories were constructed, interconnected, and eventually lost** across landscapes. We will use instances of **long-distance transport** and ‘voids’ in the archaeological record, plus correlation of **natural hazard onsets**, as potential indicators of **impacts on landscape habitation and collective memory**. To do so, the project will focus on three geographies that have the **most extensively excavated palaeolithic landscapes** in the World: **Europe, South-Eastern Africa and the Caucasus-Middle East**. Previously, I have been able to demonstrate how easily cultural practices can be lost in variable conditions(17, 18). Building on that research, CONNECTING HORIZONS aims to illuminate the otherwise inaccessible dynamics underlying the formation and dissolution of spatio-temporal connection horizons.

1.2. State-of-the-Art

CONNECTING HORIZONS's central premise is that the emergence, stability, and fragility of population connectivity can be traced archaeologically through space and time. Long-distance transport offers a unique element combining risks, communities' cognitive and physiological limits, and deep-time evidence that can be used as proxies to complex behaviours. Existing approaches in palaeoarchaeology, palaeoecology and cultural evolution often treat climate, mobility, material exchange and memory as separate domains (19). As a result, we can only describe patterns of occupation and absence, but **are not able to explain how, when and where connectivity emerged, weaned and banished**. However, thanks to recent breakthroughs in the theoretical, data and computational fronts, we can now approach the how, when and where connections persisted for tens of millennia while others collapsed abruptly by modelling how knowledge, hazards and movement co-evolved as dynamical systems. CONNECTING HORIZONS grounds the simulations on empirical evidence and builds on the achievements of the three abovementioned fields of paleohydrology, paleoclimatic extremes and biohazards, and walk-based hunter-gatherer communities to propose a radical, but necessary, focus on memory to explain the evolution of modern populations behaviour.

1.2.1. Hazards and extreme fluctuations.

Of the three research fronts, palaeoclimate is the one that most strongly requires physics-based methodologies. However, much **palaeoclimatic modelling to date has focused on mean climatic conditions**, largely because these are easier to reproduce given computational constraints and limitations in the spatial and temporal resolution of palaeoclimate data. This emphasis on averages, however, **neglects weather variability and climate extremes, which are critical drivers of human–environment interactions** but are rarely modelled due to their demanding resolution requirements. The rarity of research explicitly targeting climatic variability is underscored by the recent funding of the ERC **PIONEER** project, which combines cutting-edge climate modelling with high-resolution isotope analyses to reconstruct climate variability directly from archaeology-bearing sediments. On the purely simulating side, the CHELSA-TraCE21k model (20) offers a global dataset from the Last Glacial Maximum (21.000 yr ago) to the present. With a spatial resolution of one square kilometre, this dataset enables CONNECTING HORIZONS to analyse month-scale climatic variability at specific archaeological sites and to account for variability at the scale of three to four generations. This resolution makes it possible to examine how climatic variability itself, rather than long-term means, may have triggered regional disasters under extreme conditions, eroding otherwise suitable ecological niches.

Similarly, the study of palaeodiseases relies heavily on advances in biological and genetic sciences. **Palaeoimmunology**, in particular, is a nascent field (21, 22), enabled by recent technical developments in the recovery and sequencing of highly fragmentary genetic and proteomic material from archaeological contexts, including teeth, bones and sediment samples (23). As these datasets expand, they open new avenues for investigating past biohazards. Furthermore, growing evidence links palaeodisease dynamics to climatic and ecological stressors, including the co-occurrence of scarcity-driven malnutrition, large-scale population movements (24), and the onset of epidemics (25). CONNECTING HORIZONS analyses these often-invisible biohazards by building on recent palaeogenetic breakthroughs, alongside well-documented patterns such as the prevalence of mosquito-borne pathogens in specific landscapes (26). In doing so, the project adopts a novel palaeobiohazard perspective to investigate past population mobility and connectivity.

1.2.2 Paleolandscapes modelling.

Another research strand that relies heavily on the natural sciences is the reconstruction of ancient landscapes, specifically how landscape morphology, geology, vegetation cover and water availability shaped the mobility and connectivity of walk-based populations. **The spatio-temporal availability of palaeo hydro-refugia remains a nascent field** (27, 28) and has seen comparatively little progress when integrated into ecological niche modelling. Depending on geology and topography, the availability of groundwater, landscape corridors and surface water sources can sustain populations across the landscape, even under harsh environmental stressors. However, hydrological responses to weather and climate variability are highly non-linear, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions (29). CONNECTING HORIZONS, therefore, integrates climatic variability and hydrology by mapping proximity to water sources and their long-term reliability (27). Specifically, the project models how waterbodies are distributed across landscapes in relation to transport corridors and material sources, identifying conditions that either promote population connectivity or constrain it.

Relatedly, on the archaeological side, another key approach involves investigating the absence of archaeological remains as a potential proxy for past avoidance of specific zones. This type of inference can only be attempted in the most well-excavated regions (30), where data integration remains an issue. Previous research has shown that habitat suitability models frequently predict population presence in areas where archaeological evidence fails to corroborate those predictions. In recent years, numerous studies have analysed the ecological niches most likely occupied by past hominin species (31–33), with niche suitability further constrained using archaeologically and ethnographically informed hunting and gathering behaviours (34). CONNECTING HORIZONS' primary contribution is to introduce dynamic models capable of explaining how archaeological voids emerge, persist across space and time, and may be reoccupied in later periods, depending on how the interaction between hazards, movement and collective memory shapes landscape use. In doing so, the project transforms “absence of evidence” into a quantifiable signal of landscape avoidance driven by exposure to hazardous and highly variable environments.

1.2.3 Walk-based communities.

This research strand draws most heavily on the human sciences. Studies of memory have rarely engaged with deep-time evidence (10, 17). Building on insights from our previous project, *Cultural Loss Under Emulated Shocks* (CLUES), we now have emerging evidence that collective remembering dynamics are crucial for interpreting the past through the lens of landscape memories that are both emergent and vulnerable in a rapidly changing world (35). CLUES shifted the narrative of cultural loss as pure demographic driven, showing that plain population size might be a relatively minor factor in cultural evolution (35). CONNECTING HORIZONS contributes major advances in theory and modelling by introducing novel interpretations of archaeological data through the formal modelling of collective memory dynamics in relation to landscape variability, demographic voids, and population connectivity. When combined with rich empirical datasets, well-established geographical and environmental constraints, *in silico* modelling of populations as complex systems, and a theoretical framework centred on collective memory, this approach enables the mapping and explanation of the deep history of memory and connectivity across the planet. By modelling memory as a measurable, landscape-embedded process that both shapes and is shaped by long-distance transport, **the project establishes a new empirical methodology for reconstructing ancient memory systems.**

From the perspective of mobility, although movement and migration is widely recognised as a key component of past and present population dynamics (19, 36–40), no existing dataset or modelling framework systematically captures how materials, knowledge and people moved prior to the widespread adoption of animal-assisted or water-based transport. Research on provenance and material sourcing remains geographically constrained, focusing primarily on heavily excavated regions such as the Middle East and Caucasus (19, 41), selected European areas (42, 43), and southern Africa (44, 45). While studies of mobility patterns and social networks in forager societies do exist (40, 46–51), we still lack a comprehensive transport assessment that specifies which materials were exchanged, over what distances, by which means, for how long, and how such exchange systems emerged, stabilised, and eventually disappeared. **CONNECTING HORIZONS addresses this gap by integrating existing datasets from historical and extant walk-based populations with spatial information on resource distribution across landscapes—an underexplored yet information-rich foundation for reconstructing long-term mobility and connectivity.**

1.3. Methods & Sources: Datasets, theory, modelling

CONNECTING HORIZONS investigates the essential conditions enabling landscape connectivity and memory in places and times where the main mean of transport and movement was, or still is, walking. This approach allows relatively simple theory building and simulations to interpret available data sources and guides new data collection.

1.3.1. Data: archaeological density and cross-cultural comparison

Collecting data is often difficult because information is scattered, inconsistent or inaccessible. However, standardised and digitally available archaeological and ethnographic datasets already exist, chiefly ROAD for archaeology (52) and eHRAF for ethnography (53). CONNECTING HORIZONS combines instances from these datasets with new data by creating an integrated database of long-distance material movement, supported by the PALEOSCAPES pilot dataset (**PALEO**lithic Strategies & Corridor Analysis in **Pleistocene Environmental Sourcing**). PALEOSCAPES captures a **parallel climatic and archaeological chronology** at each site showing, chronologically: (i) relative hazard exposure; (ii) the proximity to waterbodies; (iii) materials' sources; (iv) transport corridors; (v) presence or absence of long-distance transport. These elements allow to empirically ground the archaeological record on long-distance transport and create *in silico* versions of walk-based movement.

FIG. 2 Research areas on RODES coverage map

Unfortunately, most geographies do not have a systematic and dense enough archaeological record to do this exercise at a global scale, thus, **CONNECTING HORIZONS** focuses on three geographies most extensively excavated through the rise of *Homo sapiens* to the advent of agriculture: **Europe** in the Upper Palaeolithic and Mesolithic (50.000 to 5.000 BP ago), **Southern and Eastern Africa** in the Middle to Late Stone Age (280.000 to 7.000 BP), **Caucasus-Middle East** in the Late Palaeolithic and Epipalaeolithic (100.000 to 10.000 BP).

CONNECTING HORIZONS expands the ethnographic data on walk-based societies through literature reviews and fieldwork in three regions. The ethnographic literature not always address in enough detail the needed elements, and how these change with time. To supplement these inferences, the project, plans to complement the literature with fieldwork where walk-based movement is, or was until recently, the main transport method. This work will serve as a cross reference with the instances inferred from the literature and how these have changed since recorded. The fieldwork shall be in three geographical regions characterised by being inner basins without much water transport like the Okavango and Northern Orange river basins (Botswana–Namibia–Angola–South Africa), much of the Australian interior, the North American Great Basin, or the Northern Andes.

1.3.2. Theory: and transport.

The project's theoretical basis draws on work in cultural evolution, collective memory-network dynamics, perturbation theory and Bayesian methods. Earlier research from the CLUES project provides key tools for studying cultural loss (54), while novel network-memory correlation with perturbations guides how we infer patterns from incomplete evidence to assess whether empirical voids are data artifacts or can represent meaningful evidence of absence. This *voids'* perspective further informs what to look for and how to interpret the data from an innovative, yet theoretically grounded, perspective.

The proposal links archaeological landscapes with collective memory over time, using the “gravitation-like” dynamics that govern transport, exchange and interaction alongside archaeological voids i.e. well-traversed corridors and nexus will attract more presence, while relatively sparse areas will be disconnected and shed out population. Moreover, hazards, and memories of these, might disrupt these dynamics, creating non-intuitive patterns that shall be picked up in the archaeological record. **CONNECTING HORIZONS brings these strands together to explore how collective memories, landscape, transport corridors, hazards and cultural loss shape movement, habitability, demography and behaviour over space and time.**

1.3.3. Modelling: Forgetting, movement, and hazards

Through modelling, **CONNECTING HORIZONS** maps collective-memory dynamics into long-distance transport patterns and demographic voids in otherwise suitable habitats. Memories themselves are shaped by past climatic extremes and hazards (35, 55–58). This coevolving dynamics of populations, hazards and landscape needs *in silico* reconstructions grounded in cognitive science and supported by archaeological and cross-cultural evidence on disaster-response strategies and the maintenance of long-distance links (39, 59, 60).

A key extension of this framework is the explicit incorporation of **biohazards and palaeodiseases** as drivers of connectivity and avoidance. Recent advances in palaeogenetics now allow the reconstruction of ancient pathogen distributions, transmission pathways and disease prone landscapes (26), making it possible to model how disease risk intersected with mobility, aggregation and exchange. Biohazards are modelled as shaping transport corridors, trigger long-term avoidance of otherwise viable habitats, and influence collective memory through socially transmitted risk perception.

CONNECTING HORIZONS uses agent-based modelling simulations to explore how populations move, interact and remember their landscapes under specific constraints, such as walk-based transport, mnemonic technologies and exposure to environmental and biological hazards. Collective memory is modelled as a dynamical system shaped by cognitive constraints and oral mnemonic practices, while hazards—both climatic and epidemiological—act as perturbations with distinct temporal signatures. Bringing these intertwined elements together allows us to simulate how connectivity, knowledge and risk awareness co-evolved across space and time.

1.4 Vision and Ambition

The central ambition of CONNECTING HORIZONS is to transform how we understand long-term human connectivity, cultural resilience and the transmission and loss of collective memories across landscapes. Despite major advances in palaeoarchaeology, climate science and cultural evolution, these domains remain largely disconnected. As a result, we can document where people lived and where materials moved, but we still lack a coherent explanation of how interaction networks emerged, stabilised or collapsed, how some cultural practices endured for millennia while others vanished, and how memory, mobility and hazard exposure co-evolved as coupled systems. CONNECTING HORIZONS addresses this gap by advancing a unifying vision in which **collective memory, landscape constraints and long-distance transport are treated as interdependent drivers of human history.**

The project's principal breakthrough lies in its integrated treatment of collective memories, archaeological voids, immunology, and long-distance exchange across three of the best-excavated Palaeolithic regions in the world. Rather than treating absences in the archaeological record as methodological limitations, CONNECTING HORIZONS reframes them as potential signals of disrupted connectivity, lost knowledge or remembered hazards. This shift enables a move beyond descriptive presence maps towards a **mechanistic understanding of how interaction horizons form, persist and dissolve through time.** By linking memory decay with hazard variability and transport contraction, the project introduces a predictive framework for the loss of cultural practices, skills, expertise and exchange systems—one that is directly relevant to contemporary debates on climate adaptation, governance and risk reduction.

Methodologically, CONNECTING HORIZONS represents a step change. It combines established approaches—such as niche modelling, palaeoclimate reconstruction and archaeological sourcing—with emerging tools drawn from cross-cultural studies of mnemonic systems, dynamical models of memory retention and loss, paleopathogen genetics, and fine-grained hydrological and climatic reconstructions that explicitly capture variability and extremes rather than long-term averages. This multimodal integration allows, for the first time, the development of a **mechanistic account of how walk-based societies manage long-distance transport,** sustaining or losing connectivity across space and time, grounded in both empirical data and theory.

A key ambition of the project is to establish the first global, standardised database of walk-based exchange networks. Existing research has shown that complex movement and exchange dynamics can emerge from relatively simple decision rules when populations rely on non-primary resources (19, 41). CONNECTING HORIZONS builds on this insight by systematically quantifying transport distances, exchange stability and corridor persistence across prehistoric and ethnographic contexts. This resource will provide unprecedented baselines not only for prehistoric inference, but also for contemporary sustainability science, where understanding the fragility of connectivity is increasingly urgent.

At a conceptual level, the project challenges dominant assumptions in cultural evolution and collective memory research. Where previous models have focused primarily on transmission fidelity and demography, my prior and ongoing work demonstrates that **memory decay, variability of practice, hazard exposure and connectivity stability are far more influential in determining cultural persistence or loss.** CONNECTING HORIZONS extends this perspective by embedding memory dynamics directly within spatial and environmental constraints, enabling archaeological inference about memory systems that have left no direct material trace.

Ultimately, the ambition of CONNECTING HORIZONS is not simply to reinterpret the past, but to provide a new language for thinking about human connectivity as a fragile, adaptive system. By revealing how populations in the deep past navigated environmental uncertainty, maintained long-distance ties and remembered—or forgot—critical knowledge, the project lays the foundations for a fundamentally new understanding of long-term inter-community interaction. In doing so, it offers insights that resonate far beyond archaeology, informing how we conceptualise resilience, vulnerability and cultural sustainability in an increasingly unstable world.

In sum, by precisely quantifying fluctuating connection horizons and integrating empirically grounded first principles, agent-based modelling and robust Bayesian model–data comparison, **CONNECTING HORIZONS opens a new window onto the intertwined histories of collective memory and connectivity, advancing archaeological voids from marginal absences to a central analytical lens for understanding long-term human adaptation.**

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53. eHRAF World Cultures. <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu>.
54. A. Arinyo-i-Prats, “Cultural Loss Under Bottlenecks – DEMographic, Climatic and Environmental Socks (CLUB-DECES)” in *Terra Incognita: Libro Blanco Sobre Transdisciplinariedad y Nuevas Formas de Investigación En El Sistema Español de Ciencia y Tecnología* (PressBooks, Burgos, Spain, 2020; <https://pressbooks.pub/terraincognita/chapter/arinyo-i-prats-a-combining-to-preserve-tools-to-estimate-the-resilience-against-cultural-loss/>).
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56. D. E. Alexander, Resilience and disaster risk reduction: an etymological journey. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* **13**, 2707–2716 (2013).
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58. A. Y. Rosinger, Extreme climatic events and human biology and health: A primer and opportunities for future research. *Am. J. Hum. Biol.* **35**, e23843 (2023).
59. A. C. Pisor, J. H. Jones, Do people manage climate risk through long-distance relationships? *Am. J. Hum. Biol.* **33**, e23525 (2021).
60. S. A. Crabtree, Inferring Ancestral Pueblo Social Networks from Simulation in the Central Mesa Verde. *J. Archaeol. Method Theory* **22**, 144–181 (2015).

1.6. Curriculum vitae and Track Record

EDUCATION/ACADEMIC DEGREES

MSci (informal attendance) 2019-2021

Institut de Física de Sistemes Complexos, Department of Physics, University of Illes Balears, SP

PhD 2011-2015

Institut de Ciències del Cosmos, Department of Astronomy and Meteorology, University of Barcelona, SP

MSci 2010-2011

Particle Physics Astrophysics and Cosmology –Department of Astronomy and Meteorology, University of Barcelona, SP

BA 2005-2010

Licenciate in Physical sciences –Department of Physics and Optics, University of Valencia, SP

CURRENT & MOST RECENT EMPLOYMENT

2026-

Postdoc, Department of Economics, University of Maine, US

2026- 2025

Marie Skłodowska Curie Fellow, Global Postdoc, Afdeling for Arkæologi og Kulturarvsstudier, Aarhus University, DK

2024-2025

Visiting Scholar, Associate Fellow, Max Plank Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, DE

2022-

Visiting Scholar, Associate Fellow, Simon Fraser University, Burnaby, CA

2020-2022

Postdoc, Institute of Computer Science, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prage, CZ

MANAGEMENT EXPERIENCE

2022-2024: President of the Postdoctoral Association, Simon Fraser University, CA

2021-2022: Social dynamiser for junior research staff

2011-2015: PhD representative at the Institut de Ciències del Cosmos, University of Barcelona, SP

2008-2010: Head speaker of the Association of Physics and Optics students, University of Valencia, SP

SCIENTIFIC FOCUS AREA

I am culture/knowledge-minded physicist with an intense interest in understanding the patterns and processes of human cultural evolution, especially its loss or retention in relation climatic and environmental extreme change or shocks. Inspired by cosmology, I often combine a theoretical background to develop the interface between modelling and quantitative methods to analyse large biased and multi-proxy datasets. In the cultural domain I try to bring the physics mindset to anthropology to find relevant laws of the limits of knowledge preservation – under the umbrella term of ‘anthrophysics’, which I coined. Through a career transition from Cosmology to Complex Systems, Information Theory and anthropology, and a personally driven pioneering project on Cultural Loss, I have been able to cultivate and explore interdisciplinary research environments that reach from physics to archaeology, and from climate to risk science.

INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Born and raised in Catalan-speaking Spain, and university-educated in Valencia, SP, and London, UK, I have successfully integrated in 9 different research institutions in 5 European countries and Canada across 4 different research fields. My network of collaborators is global in spread and transdisciplinary in composition.

Having published on a range of topics, I commonly give advice, inspiration and guidance to my collages and collaborators in their own lines of research and innovative topics.

I obtained the high-profile Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions-Global Fellowship grand to fund my own research.

SUPERVISION

Although I have not formally supervised any students —due to my changes in research fields—

I continuously participate in the informal guidance and assessment of my junior collages and students from my immediate supervisors and groups.

EXPLORATION AND OUTREACH

As part as broadening my scientific horizons and perspective, I engaged in extensive traveling across the Globe, with a solo traveling for 1.5 years in distant cultural landscapes, which inspired my research in cultural loss. I have written an extensive account of the experience (in process of being published, in Catalan).

As part of my research path I routinely engage in public awareness of science and exploration, dynamizing and creating outreach experiences from school to adult public, both in public events and through radio programs. At the Catalan radio I have presented two Cosmology themed and two anthropology themed episodes. I have created and coordinated physics experiments for children and teenagers at the Department of Astronomy and Meteorology, UB as well as giving talks about physics and anthropology at different high-schools.

RELEVANT MERITS**Publications**

**Corresponding Author.*

1. Arinyo-i-Prats A.* Cultural Loss Under Bottlenecks – DEMographic, Climatic and Environmental Socks (CLUB-DECES). Terra Incognita: Libro blanco sobre transdisciplinariedad y nuevas formas de investigación en el Sistema Español de Ciencia y Tecnología. Burgos, Spain: PressBooks; 2020. Available: <https://pressbooks.pub/terraincognita/chapter/arinyo-i-prats-a-combining-to-preserve-tools-to-estimate-the-resilience-against-cultural-loss/>
2. Arinyo-i-Prats A*, López-Madrona VJ, Paluš M. Lead/Lag directionality is not generally equivalent to causality in nonlinear systems: Comparison of phase slope index and conditional mutual information. *NeuroImage*. 2024;292: 120610. doi:[10.1016/j.neuroimage.2024.120610](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2024.120610)
3. Arinyo-i-Prats A*, Mas-Ribas L, Miralda-Escudé J, Pérez-Ràfols I, Noterdaeme P. A metal-line strength indicator for damped Lyman alpha (DLA) systems at low signal-to-noise. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*. 2018;481: 3921–3934. doi:[10.1093/mnras/sty2374](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty2374)
4. Arinyo-i-Prats A*, Miralda-Escudé J, Viel M, Cen R. The non-linear power spectrum of the Lyman alpha forest. *J Cosmol Astropart Phys*. 2015: 017. doi:[10.1088/1475-7516/2015/12/017](https://doi.org/10.1088/1475-7516/2015/12/017)
5. Arinyo-i-Prats A*, Moreno-Spiegelberg P, Matias MA, Gomila D. Traveling pulses in type-I excitable media. *Phys Rev E*. 2021;104: L052203. doi:[10.1103/PhysRevE.104.L052203](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.104.L052203).
6. Arinyo-i-Prats A*, Sandgathe D, Riede F, Collard M. Use it or lose it: lost in the cold, did some Neanderthal populations lose fire? A model-based assessment. *Open Res Europe*; 2025. doi:doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20477.2
7. Arinyo-i-Prats A*, Turner N, Latosky S. Rethinking Cultural Keystone Practices: Conflict resolution practices as examples of salience and well-being. *Ethnobiology Letters* 2025. doi:doi.org/10.14237/ebl.16.2.2025.1909
8. Preprint: Arinyo-i-Prats A*, Riede F, Collard M. Disastrous resonances: On the relationship between extreme events, cultural memory, and societal resilience; 2025. Book Chapter, *Climate Change in Archaeology and Heritage*. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.17857736](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17857736)
9. Mas-Ribas L*, Miralda-Escudé J, Pérez-Ràfols I, Arinyo-i-Prats A, Noterdaeme P, Petitjean P, et al. The Mean Metal-line Absorption Spectrum of Damped Ly α Systems in BOSS. *ApJ*. 2017;846: 4. doi:[10.3847/1538-4357/aa81cf](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa81cf)
10. Pérez-Ràfols I*, Miralda-Escudé J, Arinyo-i-Prats A, Font-Ribera A, Mas-Ribas L. The cosmological bias factor of damped Lyman alpha systems: dependence on metal line strength. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*. 2018;480: 4702–4709. doi:[10.1093/mnras/sty2158](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty2158)

Congresses

1. 2012 CosmoComp workshop in Trieste. Invited talk
2. 2014 Intergalactic Matters at the MPIA of Heidelberg. Contributed talk
3. 2018 Intergalactic Interconnections, Aix-Marseille Maresille. Contributed talk.
4. 2022 Complex Systems conference, Complex Systems Society (Palma de Mallorca). Session talk
5. 2023 ESHE, European Society for the study of Human Evolution (Aarhus). Plenary talk
6. 2023 Effects of unpredictable change on Human behavioural evolution, CLUES-DECEB (Aarhus).
Workshop organiser
7. 2024 SAA, Society for American Archaeology (New Orleans). Session talk
8. 2024 SoE, Society of Ethnobiology (Saint Louis)(online). Plenary talk

9. 2024 Mathematical Models in Prehistoric Cultural Evolution workshop, Mathematical Prehistory group at Meij University (Sendai). Contributed talk
10. 2025 Kiel Conference. Invited talk.

Research projects

1. BOSS (Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey): My PhD was conducted within the context of an international collaboration involving hundreds of researchers worldwide. BOSS was a collaborative effort and an instrument that measured, over a decade, the spectrum (light decomposition) of millions of galaxies and hundreds of thousands of quasars (hyper-relativistic jets originating from immense black holes at the centres of the universe's first galaxies). I regularly participated in group calls, workshops, and conferences aimed at modelling the 3D structure of the universe using massive cosmological simulations and comparing these with observational datasets.

I contributed to this project by modelling the 3D structure of the non-linear scales of the cosmos and assisted in organising a BOSS meeting at the University of Barcelona (2017). From this collaboration, I gained valuable experience in coordinating large, international research groups, understanding the importance of standardisation in measurements and definitions, and accurately characterising measurement errors. I also learned to transfer knowledge across fields, borrowing extensively from Bayesian methods developed at CERN for particle physics. Additionally, I developed an acute awareness of the need to address conceptual, methodological, and observational biases before making any claims of discovery.

2. CLIOARCH: My MSCA-GF, hosted by Aarhus University under the mentorship of Felix Riede (FR), was developed alongside FR's ERC-funded CLIOARCH project (grant number 817564), a 5-year initiative involving 2 postdoctoral researchers, 4 PhD students, 4 associated postdocs, and 12 external collaborators. During my time with CLIOARCH, I gained experience in leading, mentoring, and coordinating a diverse group of researchers from multiple disciplines, as well as in identifying new research opportunities and securing funding for them.

FR, who describes himself as a “research entrepreneur,” emphasises the importance of thinking outside the box, seizing opportunities, managing time effectively, strengthening collaborations, and honing writing and communication skills. Particular attention was given to visuals and organising regular coordination events, such as retreats, workshops, dinners, and social activities.

My contributions to the project include integrating the focus on disasters and extreme events with the work of student Laurits Andreasen, brainstorming and refining ideas that secured funding for a gene-culture coevolution project, organising social events like paella cooking, and leading a group retreat.